
ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effects of social networking sites on the academic performance of the students as related to the socio-demographic characteristics, social networking site usage and social network addiction. As to the socio-demographic characteristics, the respondents' age ranged from 15-17 years old or 70% of the total number of respondents. A big proportion of 70% were females. Most of the respondents were single with 98%. Their family income ranged from P5,000-9,999 with 43%. Most of the respondents were form BSED I-B which garnered 72% of the total number of respondents. The respondents' average hours of active internet use per day is one hour with 35%. Most of the respondents had facebook accounts with 70% and had 10-49 connections/friends in their profile. Out of 50 respondents 50% percent do not have community group membership in their favorite social networking sites. The respondents logged on to their account once a week with 30% and another 30% occasionally signed in to their favorite social network service. A big proportion of the respondents with 64% spent an average one hour in their favorite social networking site per session. The survey revealed that 66% of the respondents are most likely not addicted to social media.

KEYWORDS: Social Networking, Academic Performance, First Year BSED Students, Naval State University.

INTRODUCTION

With the rapid phase of the changing generation, the youth is now more demanding in acquiring technologies that with fit to their needs, especially when it is applied to their studies. Certainly, the access in internet or in the World Wide Web is easy and there are many benefits to be gained.

Everyday, millions - if not billions of people around the world use social networking sites to connect with friends they've never met and business contact they've never seen. But many people question questions the effects of internet social networking on our lives and wonder what, if any, are negative effects of this new technology. The advent of social networking sites, like Facebook and MySpace (among others) has made it far easier for us to stay in touch with the people we met before and to stay up to date on the events happening in the lives of people you would have lost touch with otherwise.

According to an Article on Health Guidance.org, "in the case of sites such as Facebook and other then, you're actually more in contact with people than you would be otherwise and in fact need never lose contact with anyone ever again". Due to the continuous change in cultural and social aspect and with the accordance of technological revolution, the social networking's essence in the face of the internet and web is still in question.

Now, ask every student and they will definitely tell you that they had an account ranges from 1-3 in different social networking sites. With this fact, the networking sites are subject for scrutiny because it may contribute influences to the individuals especially college students. Because of the prevailing reasons aforementioned, the researchers are determined to unveil the effects of social networking sites to the students' academic performance.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study generally aimed to find out the effects of social networking sites to the academic performance of the first year secondary education students of Naval State University. Specifically, it sought to answer the following objectives:

1. Determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Civil Status
 - 1.4 Monthly Income; and
 - 1.5 Year and Section

2. Determine the social networking site usage of the students in terms of:
 - 2.1 Average hour of active internet use per day
 - 2.2 Social networking profile
 - 2.3 Average connections of students in their social networking site
 - 2.4 Number of communities/group of students
 - 2.5 Frequency visit to social network services
 - 2.6 Favorite social networking site usage per session

3. Determine the students' addiction to social networking sites and effects of it to their academic performance.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on theories propounded by Albert Bandura, B. F. Skinner and Abraham Maslow. Bandura's Social Learning Theory, as social media made inroads into our living rooms, much of social learning has been influenced by it, especially among the impressionable minds of children and adolescents. Adolescents have the most impressionable minds, which explains their ability to learn and comprehend and quickly pick up behaviors from their surrounding environment. Behavior patterns do not necessarily have to be taught to them - they are highly receptive to learning through social networking.

As media and its various forms have gradually intruded into most households, social learning theories have identified the influence of media in shaping the social behavior of adolescent and children. Social networking sites are virtual worlds for the internet users. Spending so much time in the virtual worlds affects the academic learning abilities of young minds and the behavior of these youths. It is from the constant exposure to and interaction in the virtual world as well as through chatting and video sharing that students pick up many of their characteristics traits. There behavioral traits, learned as young adults, continue throughout adulthood. These are potential influences of social learning patterns seen in grownups.

B. F. Skinner Operant Conditioning Theory is based upon the idea that learning is function of change in overt behavior. Changes in behavior are the result of an individual's response to events that occur in the environment. In the case of students who are engaging in social networking sites, the reason why students are addicted to modern social media is the stimulus or the environment that drive them to practice such.

Psychological theory of needs theorized by Abraham Maslow pointed out that humans need to feel a sense of belonging and acceptance, whether it comes from a large social group, such as clubs, office culture, religious groups, professional organizations, sports teams, gangs, small social connections or even social networking sites. They need to be love and be loved by others. In the absence of these elements, many people become susceptible to loneliness, social anxiety, and clinical depression.

Behaviorist theorized that learning occurs through interactions with the environments. Two other assumptions of this theory are that the environment shapes behavior and that taking internal mental states such as thoughts, feelings and emotions into considerations is useless in explaining behavior.

The Theoretical Framework is best presented in Figure 1.

Figure1. Theoretical Framework of the Study

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study conceptualized that socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and social networking site usage are related to the academic performance and behavioral alterations of the students. The theories cited in this research such reached a common point in supporting the variables indicated.

As mentioned, respondents' academic performance and behavioral alterations are determined by their socio-demographic characteristics. Age which is affected by individual's maturity, gender, and civil status and family income has something to do with their participation in modern social media.

Social networking site usage is conceived to be related with respondents' participation in social networking. Socialization through cyber media could spell great significance in this study. All aforementioned variables significantly affect the academic performance and low study habits of the students. The Conceptual Framework of the study is best presented in figure 2.

Figure2. Conceptual Framework of the study

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents an overview of how this study was undertaken. It describes the operational design which embraces all approaches and procedures to be use in the conduct of the study or in the realization of its design, research locale, research subjects, research instruments, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment of data. Explanatory study was used in this research, method attempts to explain the possible factors related to a problem that may associate with the occurrence of the problem. The research was conducted in the College of Education at Naval State University, Naval, Biliran. This study focus on freshmen BSED students as the respondents of this study.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Year and Section	Number of Respondents
BSED I-A	12
BSED I-B	36
BSED I-C	2
TOTAL	50

The table shows that the study covers the three sections of first year BSED department. BSED I- A, BSED I-B, and BSED I-C had twelve, thirty six and two respondents respectively. Fifty respondents were surveyed through answering the survey questionnaires provided by the researcher.

The major instruments used in the data gathering were survey questionnaires prepared by the researcher based on the existing literature in the specific field of study. To facilitate the preparation of the questionnaires, the researchers made use of materials such as books, reports, and information on the internet especially those prepared by the researchers as expanded knowledge and understanding not only for the preparation of the instruments but also in the conduct of the whole research.

There were two sets of questionnaires to be answered by the respondents. Part I focuses on the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and their social net working sites usage and Part II talks about social networking addiction and behavioral aberration.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter present the analysis, findings and interpretation of data. Tables were used in the interpretation of data. All findings were analyzed based on the specific questions stated.

Socio-Demographic Characteristics

The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents were considered in this study included gender, age, civil status, and family income.

Table 2. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent (N=50)
Gender		
Male	15	30%
Female	35	70%
Age		
15-17 years old	35	70%
18-20 years old	10	20%
21-25 years old	5	10%
More then 25	-	
Civil Status		
Single	49	98%
Married	1	2%
Widow/er	-	
Family Income		
5,000-9,999	43	86%
10,000-19,999	5	10%
20,000-29,999	2	4%
30,000 or more	-	
Year and Section		
BSED I-A	12	24%
BSED I-B	36	72%
BSED I-C	2	4%

The data on table 2 shows the socio-demographic profile of the respondents. Out of 50 respondents majority are females with 70% and 30% are males. About the age of the respondents, 70% of the age are coming from 15-17 years old age bracket, 20% are coming from 18-20 years old age bracket, 10% are coming from 18-20 years old age bracket and none of them belongs to the age bracket of 21-25 and more than 25 years old. The civil status of the respondents were 98% are single and 2 percent were married and nobody from the respondents answer widow/er. For the family income, 86% of the respondents income are coming from 5,000-9,999 income bracket, 10% are coming from 10,000-

19,999 income bracket, 4% belongs to 20,000-29,999 income bracket and none belongs to 30,000 or more income bracket. For the year and section of the respondents, 72% answers are coming from BSED I-B, 24% are coming from BSED I-A and 4% are coming from BSED I-C.

Social Networking Sites Usage

Table 3. Average hours of active internet use by the respondents/day

Hours	<i>f</i>	%
1	35	70
2	12	24
3	1	2
4	1	2
5	1	2
5 and above	0	0
Total	50	100

The results shows that 70% of the respondents had an average active internet use of one (1) hour per day; 24% had an average of 2 hours per day in the use of internet, 2% of the respondents had an average internet use of three, four and five respectively hours per day and none of the respondents answer on the internet use beyond 5 hours per day.

Social Networking profile

Table 4. Social Networking Profile of the Respondents

Networking Site	<i>f</i>	%
Facebook	49	98
LinkedIn	-	-
Twitter	-	-
Friendster	1	2
Youtube	-	-
Blogger.com	-	-
Myspace	-	-
Xing	-	-
Bebo	-	-
Flicker	-	-
Live Journal	-	-
Total	50	100

The data shows that 98% of the respondents had facebook accounts/ and only 2% of the respondents currently have friendster accounts. On the other hand, none of the respondents are affiliated to LinkedIn; Twitter; Youtube; Blogger.com; Myspace; Xing; Bebo; Flicker; and Live Journal.

Average connections of students in their social networking site

Table 5. Respondents Average Number of Connections

Number of Friends	<i>f</i>	%
Less than 10	0	0
10-49	20	40
50-99	18	36
100+	3	6
200+	9	18
Total	50	100

Table 5 revealed that 40% of the respondents had 10-49 online friends in their favorite social networking sites; 36% of the respondents had 50-99 connections; 6% of the respondents had 100 plus connections; 18% had 200 plus friends. On the other hand, none of the respondents possess less than 10 friends or connections in the social networking sites.

Number of communities/groups of students

Table 6. Respondents Number of Membership

Number of Group/Community Membership	<i>f</i>	%
None	25	50
Up to 10	21	42
11-50	1	2
51+	3	6
Total	50	100

Table 6 shows that 50% of the respondents don't have group membership in any affiliated social networking sites; 42% had up to 10 community membership; 6% of the respondents possessed 51 plus group membership and only 2% of the respondents had 11-50 group membership in their favorite social networking site.

Frequency log to social network services

Table 7. Frequency Visit to Social Networking Site

Frequency Visit	<i>f</i>	%
I'm constantly logged on	5	10
Several times a day	6	12
Once in a few days	9	18
Once a week	15	30
Occasionally (less than once a week)	15	30
Total	50	100

Table 7 revealed that 30% of the respondents logged on to their account once a week; another 30% occasionally logged on for less than once a week; 18% of the respondents visited their profile once in a few days; 12% of the respondents signed in to their social network services several times a day and 10% of the respondents constantly logged on to their profile.

Favorite social networking site usage per session

Table 8. Respondents Average Time Spent in Social Networking Site

Average Time Spent	<i>f</i>	%
Less than 1 hour	10	20
1 hour	32	64
2 hours	5	10
3 hours	1	2
4 hours	2	4
5 hours	0	0
5 hours and above	0	0
Total	50	100

Table 8 data revealed that 64% of the respondents spent one hour in their preferred social network services; 20% spent less than one hour; 10% indulged two hours in social networking; 4% spent an average time of four hours and 2% of the respondents spent three hours in average. While none of the respondents spend five hours and more than five hours spend in the social networking site.

Table 9. Respondents Social Networking Addiction Scoring

Number of "yes"	Rating
1-4	Most likely not addicted
5-8	Maybe addicted
9 above	Likely to be addicted

Table 10. Respondents Social Networking Addiction Scale

Rating	f	%
Most likely not addicted	33	66
May be addicted	15	30
Likely to be addicted	2	4
Total	50	100

Table 8-9 revealed that those who answered "yes" to between one and four questions were rated as most likely not addicted to social networking sites. Respondents who answered "yes" to between five and eight questions were rated as may be addicted to social networking sites. While those who answered "yes" between nine or more questions were rated as likely to be addicted to social networking sites.

The survey revealed that 66% of the respondents were most likely not addicted to social media; 30% may be addicted and 4% were likely to be addicted to social networking sites.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study shows that most of the respondents are female dominated; they are already mature as shown in their age. Majority of the respondents are single with most of them are coming from the income bracket of 5,000-9,999 with majority of the respondents are BSED I-B students. The respondents average use of internet per day is one hour with majority have facebook accounts. Most of the respondents have 10-49 connections or friends in their social network accounts. The respondents do not have community/group membership in their social networking sites. Some of the respondents logged on to their social networking site once a week and some signed in to their account occasionally. Majority of the respondents spent one hour session in the net and most of the respondents are likely not addicted to social networking site.

RECOMMENDATION

In consonance with the conclusions of the study the following recommendations are forwarded. First, that every individual should recognize underlying problems that may support ones social networking addiction and should strengthen relationship with friends in real life. Second, that individual must modify ones internet use step by step and computer use should be monitored and set clear limits. Third, every individual must set reasonable internet use goals and stick to them and routine to break social networking site usage patterns should be altered. Fourth, seek out friends and acquaintances who " couldn't care less" about the internet and should connect to the offline world. Lastly, internet should be treated as a significant tool in education rather than purely self entertainment and manage the internet and computer use in a useful way.

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